

Impacts of Ethno-Chemistry-Based-Approach on Achievement and Retention in Separation Techniques Concept among Secondary School Chemistry Students in Edo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated Impacts of Ethno-Chemistry-Based-Approach on Achievement and Retention in Separation Techniques Concept among Secondary School Chemistry Students in Edo State, Nigeria. This study adopted quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group research. The population of the study was 5,676 Senior Secondary School one (SSI) Chemistry students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State; out of which a sample of 64 students were purposefully selected using random sampling techniques. The instrument for data collection was Chemistry Separation Techniques Achievement Test (CSTAT) with the reliability value of 0.77 using Kuder-Richardson (KR-20). Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistics. The study revealed that students taught separation techniques using ethno-chemistry-based-approach had significantly higher mean achievement scores and higher mean retention scores compared to their counterparts taught using Lecture Method. This implies that ethno-chemistry-based-approach can improve the achievement of secondary school chemistry students and give them better retention compared to the Lecture Method. It was recommended that ethno-chemistry-based-approach should be incorporated into the curriculum design, alongside traditional methods and be used by the teachers to ensure effective delivery of Chemistry classroom instruction.

Keywords: Achievement, ethno-chemistry-based-approach, retention, separation techniques.

Introduction

Chemistry is a branch of pure science concerned with the study of structure, composition, properties and uses of matter and the forces that join their molecules together. Its significance in everyday life is undeniable, as it plays a pivotal role in areas such as food production and preservation, medicine, agriculture, and environmental sustainability. This makes Chemistry an essential part of life as it cuts across all aspects of life. Bertozzi, C. (2022) stated that Life itself is the greatest evidence of nature's highest ability to construct chemical complexity. The spectacular molecular structures located in living organisms such as plants and animals have triggered researchers to try to construct the same molecules artificially. Imitating natural molecules has often also been an important part in the development of pharmaceuticals, because many of them have been inspired by natural substances. Chemistry is often referred to as the central science because of its integration with other sciences like physics, biology and earth science. Given its importance, Chemistry should be taught in a way that students should have a deep understanding of the concept, rather than passive absorption of information. However, many secondary school students find chemistry abstract and difficult to understand, often due to ineffective teaching methods.

The challenges affecting students' understanding of chemistry include inadequate teaching methods, limited time for practical sessions, lack of student interest, and insufficient laboratory facilities. These factors are reflected in poor academic achievement of students in chemistry as seen in the West African Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) results from 2013 to 2024 shown in the table below:

Table 1. WASSCE 2013-2024 Chemistry Students Result

Year	Percentage of Students with a credit in Chemistry WASSCE	Trend
2013	58.2%	Steady
2014	56.7%	Slight diminish
2015	54.3%	Moderate diminish
2016	52.1%	Further decline
2017	50.8%	Gradual decline
2018	49.2%	drastic decrease
2019	47.5%	Notable decrease
2020	45.9%	Further decrease
2021	43.8%	Noticeable decrease
2022	41.5%	Significant decrease
2023	39.7%	drastic decrease
2024	38.1%	Notable decrease

From the table above, it was noticed that between 2013 and 2016 there was a decline in the percentage of students who passed with a credit in chemistry from 58.2% in 2013, to 52.1% in 2016. A drastic decrease in student performance was noted between 2017 and 2024, from 50.8% in 2017 to 38.1% in 2024 with the COVID-19 pandemic exacerbating the situation in 2019 to 2021. In 2022, the WAEC result recorded a significant decrease of 41.5%. And in 2024, there was a noticeable decrease in students' performance with only 38.1% students had credit in the WASSCE examination, marking a continued trend of fluctuating performance. To address this, ethno-chemistry—the study of chemical ideas within cultural contexts—has been suggested as a way to improve students' understanding of chemistry.

Ethno-chemistry as stated by Said-Ador (2017), is the chemical concepts embedded in social customs, which can help make abstract chemistry concepts more relatable and concrete for students. By integrating chemicals and practices from local cultures, students may find chemistry more engaging and easier to comprehend. This approach, termed ethno-chemistry-based-approach, involves teaching chemistry through cultural practices and familiar materials to make the subject more relevant to students' daily lives.

Ethno-chemistry-based-approach to teaching is a means of organizing chemistry instruction based on diverse cultural context. In other words, ethno-chemistry-based-approach is the process of teaching chemistry through the use of students'

cultural ideology, to gain better insight on how to manage and explain recurring situations and challenges that may show-up in their immediate domain. According to Ahmad and Halliru (2022), it is an instructional method that employs the chemistry related experiences and ideas embedded in the learners' cultural heritage and surrounding to expatiate on chemistry concepts while delivering classroom instruction. The main essence of this indigenous-based-approach is to create a link between the school setting euro-centric chemistry teaching strategies and native knowledge or cultural ideas to teach chemistry concepts thereby yielding positive results in learners' academic achievement. This idea is centred on Border Crossing theory propounded by Glien Aikenhead. According to Aikenhead (2001), border crossing is the process of moving between the cultures of different worlds. It predicts that students tend to cross a virtual border between their home culture and the culture of school-science when in the science classroom. Seiki, Domínguez and Asato (2021), as inspired by Aikenhead and Elliot (2010), discovered that for students to succeed academically, there is need for them to learn first from happenings around their homes —without prior help from their teacher—after which they can cross a cultural border from their cultural ideology to academic knowledge of school science. Unfortunately, most students found it difficult to do so. Instead, they felt cut-off by the euro-centric science, because they don't have enough quality that can make them to be identified as scientists. This implies that students learning school science are required to transcend from the knowledge acquired through natural science, imbibed in their culture to that of school science in the classroom setting (as in formal education). Bhaskar Upadhyay (2023) emphasized that science cultural border crossing in the classroom setting has to do with discerning teachers', learners' and science's cultural heritage to ensure science teaching-learning process line up with natural nature of science and solely focus on learners' interest.

Achievement refers to the extent to which students have met specific educational goals, and it is often measured by outcomes such as grade point averages. Retention, on the other hand, is the ability to store and recall learned information over time. Effective retention is not merely achieved through rote memorization but requires the use of appropriate teaching methods. Ogbeba and Ajayi (2016) emphasized that retention and achievement are closely related, as retention is identified as a critical component of successful learning.

Separation techniques, a key concept in SS1 chemistry, involve methods used to separate mixtures into their constituent elements or compounds. These techniques (including evaporation, filtration, and distillation) are essential for both learners and the society, as they are used in processes like water purification, drug production, and chemical analysis. However, despite the practical importance of these techniques, many students struggle to retain the knowledge over time. The study therefore integrated ethno-chemistry ideas related to some selected method of separation techniques (such as evaporation, filtration and distillation) in teaching chemistry.

Over the last decade, educators, parents, guardians and the general public have been disturbed by the poor performance of Chemistry students in both internal and external examinations (Olorundare, 2014). One of the reasons identified by some researchers is that Chemistry taught in most secondary schools in recent times has its foundation laid on western culture and this has little or no meaning to the students; as it looks more abstract to them. This continuous retrogression regularly observed in the academic achievement among Chemistry students could also be traced to the application of non-innovative and activity-based strategies which has taken over the use of traditional teaching methods such as lecture method that does not incorporate students' cultural ideology and experience into teaching-learning process (Oluwatosin, Emmanuel and Peter, 2017). However, there have been ongoing researches to find possible means to improve students' achievements and retention in chemistry, one of which is by integrating ethno-chemistry-based-approach into teaching the subject. Possibly the identified chemical ideas embedded in culture approach can impact chemistry teaching and give students better understanding of chemistry concepts, thereby reducing mass failure experienced almost every year in chemistry external examination.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to explore whether the ethno-chemistry-based-approach can improve the achievement and retention in separation techniques among secondary school chemistry students in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. The study specifically seeks to:

1. Determine Impacts of ethno-chemistry-based-approach on achievement in separation techniques among secondary school chemistry students in Egor, Edo State
2. Determine Impacts of ethno-chemistry-based-approach on retention in separation techniques among secondary school chemistry students in Egor, Edo State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught separation techniques using ethno-chemistry-based-approach and those taught using lecture method in Egor, Edo State?
2. What is the difference in the mean retention scores of students taught separation techniques using ethno-chemistry-based-approach and those taught using lecture method in Egor, Edo State?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught separation techniques using ethno-chemistry-based-approach and those taught using lecture method in Egor, Edo State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught separation techniques using ethno-chemistry-based-approach and those taught using lecture method in Egor, Edo State.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group design. The target population consisted of 5,676 Senior Secondary School one (SSI) Chemistry students from Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. A sample of 64 students was purposefully selected using random sampling techniques. The experimental group (ethno-chemistry-based-approach) included 34 students while the control group (lecture method) comprised 30 students. The instrument for data collection was the Chemistry Separation Techniques Achievement Test (CSTAT) which consisted of 20 multiple choice objective questions derived from WASSCE and NECO examination past questions.

A table of specifications was also employed to ensure the questions were aligned with the lesson contents. Additionally, a lesson plan was developed for teaching the separation techniques using the ethno-chemistry-based-approach. To ensure validity, the CSTAT, lesson plans, research questions, and hypotheses were reviewed by two lecturers from the Departments of Curriculum and Instructional Technology and a measurement and evaluation specialist at the University of Benin, Edo State. A secondary school chemistry teacher also reviewed the instruments for further practical relevance.

The reliability of the CSTAT was established using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20). KR-20 was used because it is suitable for determining the internal consistency of dichotomously scored instruments, where the item is scored '0' (wrong) and '1' (right). CSTAT was administered to 20 SS1 chemistry students (outside the population of the study) for trial testing, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.77.

The experiment involved two phases: (1) training of the research assistants; and (2) teaching the experimental and control groups, which was conducted by an experienced chemistry teacher. For the experimental group, the lesson was introduced by linking the ethno-chemistry-based-approach to familiar cultural practices. The teacher began by presenting everyday materials such as palm fronds, palm wine, and table salt, all derived from the students' local environment, and demonstrated cultural practices related to these materials. Students were encouraged to think about daily activities involving separation techniques and to relate these to their indigenous knowledge. The teacher corrected misconceptions and linked cultural practices to scientific principles. The initial introduction by the teacher was followed by presenting ethno-chemistry related materials such as palm fronds, palm wine and table salt gathered from students' local environment and demonstrated daily cultural practices where these materials are used. The teacher then allowed the students to think of day-to-day activities they engage in, which involves the use of separation techniques and present those other daily cultural practices or activities related to the separation techniques. Also, Students were allowed to discuss some of the cultural practices that involve separation techniques. The teacher observed and took time to explain the practices demonstrated by the students in relation to separation techniques. At this point, he corrected their mistakes by sorting out the materials compatible with science during students' presentation and changed their misconception on some cultural practices that were not compatible with science. In subsequent classes, video clips demonstrating the local production of dry gin (via distillation) and traditional production of table salt (via evaporation and filtration) were shown to the students. The video clips helped clarify the scientific concepts through culturally relevant examples. Students were then allowed to interact, ask questions, and clear any misconceptions related to the lesson, making the learning process student-centered. At the end of each lesson, the teacher summarized the key points, ensuring students' understanding by linking their indigenous knowledge to scientific concepts. Retention was further tested through periodic evaluation and re-evaluation via questions and assignments on relevant separation techniques.

In contrast, the control group was taught using the lecture method. Here, the teacher presented the content through in-depth explanations and provided lengthy notes for students to copy. Students were allowed to ask questions, but the teaching approach was teacher-centered, compared to the student-centered ethno-chemistry-based-approach used in the experimental group.

Data generated through this study were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test statistical methods. The decision rule was to reject the null hypothesis if the p-value was less than or equal to 0.05 ($P \leq 0.05$) and to retain the null hypothesis if the p-value was greater than 0.05 ($P > 0.05$).

The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistics.

Results

The results of this study were presented in the tables according to the research questions and their corresponding hypotheses:

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught separation techniques using ethno-chemistry-based-approach and those taught using lecture method in Egor, Edo State?

Table 2: t-test analysis of Post-Test Mean Achievement scores for Experimental and Control groups of Students taught Separation Techniques using Ethno-chemistry-based-approach and Lecture Method

S/N	Variable Name	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
34	Experimental	6.38	2.47	15.35	2.46	8.97
30	Control	6.60	2.87	12.30	2.56	5.70
	Mean difference	0.22		3.05		3.27

At significant of $p \leq 0.05$

The result in Table 2 revealed that, the overall mean difference between the two groups was 3.27 in favour of the experimental group. The experimental group, taught using the Ethno-chemistry-based-approach, achieved a mean post-test score of 15.35 with a mean gain of 8.97, while the control group, taught using the Lecture Method, had a mean post-test score of 12.30 with a mean gain of 5.70. The mean score of 3.27 is in favour of the experimental group. This suggests that students in the experimental group outperformed those in the control group, implying that the Ethno-chemistry-based-approach was more effective.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in the mean retention scores of students taught separation techniques using ethno-chemistry-based-approach and those taught using lecture method in Egor, Edo State?

Table 3: t-test analysis of post-test Mean Retention scores for experimental and control groups of Students taught Separation Techniques using Ethno-chemistry-based-approach and Lecture Method

S/N	Variable Name	PRE-TEST		RETENTION-TEST		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
34	Experimental	6.38	2.47	13.35	3.09	6.97
30	Control	6.60	2.87	10.60	2.17	4.00
	Mean difference	0.22		2.75		2.97

At significant of $p \leq 0.05$

Table 3 reveals the t-test analysis of post-test mean retention scores for the experimental and control groups. The experimental group achieved a mean retention score of 13.35 with a mean gain of 6.97, while the control group had a mean retention score of 10.60 with a mean gain of 4.00. The mean score of 2.97 is in favour of the experimental group. This suggests that students in the experimental group also had better retention of the concepts compared to the control group.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught separation techniques using ethno-chemistry-based-approach and those taught using lecture method in Egor, Edo State.

Table 4: t-test analysis result for Mean Achievement scores of Students taught Separation Techniques using Ethno-chemistry-based-approach and Lecture Method

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig (2-tailed)	Decision
34	Experimental	15.3529	2.46	4.859	.001	H ₀ Rejected
30	Control	12.3000	2.56			

At significant of $p \leq 0.05$

Table 4 presents the t-test analysis of the mean achievement scores showing a t-value of 4.859 with a p-value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05. This indicates a statistically significant difference in the academic achievement scores between the two groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught separation techniques using ethno-chemistry-based-approach and those taught using lecture method in Egor, Edo State

Table 5: t-test analysis for Mean Retention scores of Students taught Separation Techniques using Ethno-chemistry-based-approach and Lecture Method

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
34	Experimental	13.3529	3.09	4.066	.002	H ₀ Rejected
30	Control	10.6000	2.18			

At significance of $P \leq 0.05$

Table 5 shows the t-test analysis of the mean retention scores, with a t-value of 4.066 and a p-value of 0.002 which is also less than 0.05. This indicates a significant difference in the retention scores between the two groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This concludes that the experimental group, taught using the ethno-chemistry-based-approach, had significantly better retention than the control group.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study reveal that students taught separation techniques using Ethno-chemistry-based-approach had significantly higher mean achievement and retention scores than their counterparts who were taught the same concept using the lecture method. A possible explanation for this result is that Ethno-chemistry-based-approach assisted students to link their indigenous ideology, background and immediate environment with the formal school learning system in the classroom. When learners connect day-to-day cultural activities to school chemistry concepts, they were able to understand the topic (separation techniques) better than when they took in information passively through Lecture Method. Another reason for the enhanced achievement and retention among the students in the experimental group could be their familiarity with local cultural resources, available in their environment. This is as a result of the availability of these resources in the learners' domain, which were more accessible to students, thereby making learning more practical and less abstract, as the materials were part of their world. Therefore, students could make use of these cultural resources effortlessly at any point to reinforce the chemistry concepts acquired.

These findings aligned with the results of previous studies. For instance, Ezeanya (2023) found that students taught Chemistry using the Ethno-Chemistry Instructional Approach had significantly higher retention scores than those taught through conventional lecture methods. This study also supports the findings of Ajayi et al. (2017), as well as Abunchukwu et al. (2021), both of which observed that students in the experimental group, taught using the Ethno-chemistry-based-approach, had higher mean scores compared to their control group counterparts. This is in line with the findings of Indra and Bitwell (2016) who reported that incorporating ethno-chemistry practices into Chemistry teaching significantly improved secondary school students' attitude toward the subject. It supported findings from another research which shows that ethno-chemistry-based-approach could easily develop student involvement in relating chemical concepts with day-to-day activities, which will

in turn give deeper understanding of chemistry and improve students' learning experience (Rahmawati et al., 2017a; Wahyudiati, 2021). This is in accordance with some findings which revealed that ethno-chemistry-based experimental approach provides actual and concrete experiences to expands the capability to analyze and provide lasting solution that will have positive influence on students learning outcomes (Gunawan et al. 2020; Sumardi & Wahyudiati, 2022; Sutrisno et al., 2020; Wahyudiati et al., 2022).

In summary, the results revealed that students taught separation techniques using the Ethno-chemistry-based-approach not only have higher academic achievement but also have higher retention of information better than those taught using the Lecture Method. This could be as a result of the active involvement of students in the learning process, which makes learning to be more of learner centred and less of teachers centred. The Ethno-chemistry-based-approach encourages students to think critically, experiment, and find solutions to problems using their cultural knowledge and practices, creating a more engaged and interactive learning experience. This contrasts with the passive nature of the Lecture Method, where students are merely passive in receiving classroom instruction.

The findings further highlight the significant role that students' cultural backgrounds and practices play in shaping their attitudes toward learning and their academic performance. Students tend to perform better and retain more information when allowed to integrate their cultural knowledge into problem-solving, as established by Ann (2012). Her research found that students who could link their existing cultural knowledge to learning problems had higher retention capacity than those who were passive learners in a traditional, teacher-centred learning environment.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that the Ethno-chemistry-based-approach significantly enhances students' academic achievement and retention in the teaching of separation techniques compared to the traditional Lecture Method. By allowing students to connect their indigenous knowledge and cultural practices with formal learning in the school setting, it will enhance students' understanding and retention of the subject. This shows that Ethno-chemistry-based-approach can foster a deeper understanding and more active engagement of learners in the teaching-learning process. The findings align with previous research, highlighting the importance of cultural relevance in education, where students' familiarity with local materials and practices not only aids comprehension but also enhances retention.

Recommendation

In view of the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Students should be actively involved in the process of teaching and be allowed to make contributions based on their cultural knowledge and daily cultural practices, rather than being passively involved in the classroom. This will make learning more of learner centered and less of teacher centered.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to adopt ethno-chemistry-based-approach in teaching separation techniques in chemistry, as it will link students' cultural knowledge with foreign system of teaching in the classroom, thereby give them better understanding of chemistry concepts
3. Training should be organized for the in-service Chemistry teachers to update them on the use of Ethno-chemistry-based-approach and how they can easily integrate it into the teaching-learning process.
4. The curriculum planner should incorporate ethno-chemistry-based-approach in the curriculum design to teach separation techniques and ensure the teachers use it alongside conventional methods, in delivering classroom instruction.
5. Examination bodies (WAEC, NECO), ministry of education and professional bodies such as Association of Science Educators (ASE) and Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should endeavour to organize conferences or seminars and workshops to generalize and sensitize chemistry teachers on the incorporation of ethno-chemistry-based-approach in teaching chemistry concepts in Nigerian secondary schools.

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